
Project: *Global Baroque: transcultural and transhistorical approaches to Latin America*

METROPOLITAN CATHEDRAL'S FACADE AND THE POLITICAL SPEECH

Klency Kakazu de Brito Yang

When Hernan Cortés arrived in Tenochtitlan (1511), the capital of the Aztec Empire and met Motezuma II, he witnessed an old civilization that remained alive and became its butcher. Indeed, Cortés wasn't intending the end of that civilization; he was looking for wealth and was finding a way to take the treasure behind it.

Being there at the Aztec *teocalli*, Cortés set an altar with the cross and the Virgin Mary image, and the first *Te Deum* was celebrated, and then begun the end of that civilization. The first Christian church was built over the ruins of the Aztec temple.

The architectural program followed was the roman's plan learnt by Sixto V: "*Roma el prototipo de la unidad fundamental de la arquitectura barroca: la ciudad capital.*"¹. Sixto V followed after Pio IV, was the pope of the Council of Trent (1562-1563) that established the Protestant Reformation.

Every city need a central place like a *piazze* where the religious power is spread for the community, "*La red urbana resultante no se organiza en torno a un centroid principal sino que une multitude de centros, tanto edificios como piazze.*"²

The *Piazza del Popolo*, *Piazza San Pietro* and *Piazza Novona* are examples of this kind of organization. The *Piazza Novona* was a political area since the Imperor Domiciano (86 B.C.) and is part of the architecture Baroque at Roma, where we can see the church, the obelisk and the political buildings around an open area that establishes the political power center.

The Metropolitan Cathedral in Mexico is located in the Mexican political power. And there is an open park area where the people can testimony the most important palaces: the political and religious meeting point; and in the middle of the park there is a Mexican Nacional Flag.

Streets are concentrating or dispersing from this important place: "*... las calles radials, ya se concentren o se dispersen respect a un lugar importante.*"³

The Metropolitan Cathedral is the palace of the catholic religion at Mexico City and when was set it was in the presence of the Catholic King⁴ and after his victory over the natives' paganism. And when the

¹ NOBERG-SCHULZ, Christian. *Arquitectura Barroca*. Madrid: Aguilar, 1972, p. 15

² *Ibidem*, p.27

³ *Ibidem*, p. 29

rebuilding happened in 1536, the royal determination was "*conociéndose el estado de la iglesia que debiera ser la más insigne*"⁵. About importance of this Cathedral we have an explanation gave by Gauvin (2005):

Cathedral were also the largest structure ever built in the colonial era. Not surprisingly, the Crown paid close attention to the cathedral architecture, spending great sums of money hiring teams of professional architects from Spain and Portugal, approving plans and elevations with their royal seals, and closely monitoring construction, making alterations as fashion changed and techniques improved. Like viceregal civic architecture, cathedrals were built in a strictly European style, at the beginning in the same austere, Renaissance manner inspired by the Italian manuals...⁶

The cathedral façade follow the three vertical sections and flanked by two towers⁷, and has the influence of the Plateresque (is formed by clusters of elaborate, intricate, often floral decoration)⁸. They have an influence of a kind of Islamic art that was current in Spain in that time and the ceiling has Gothic esthetic different from the façade due to two different generations of the masons.⁹ The Baroque *estípite* is the use of pyramidal form upside down, and is an abstraction of the human body.¹⁰

The Cathedral Metropolitana in 1585 started the large building construction and Claudio de Arciniega was in charge of this work, the principal entrance was a work done by Alonso Pablo, Juan de Artega and Hérnam Garcia de Villaverde with the support of the stone expert Martin Casillas, followed of the Classic Style design.¹¹ Arciniega design the Cathedral as the New Salamanca's Cathedral.¹²

The north entrance followed the Mexican classicism with clean and full arc construction. The oriental tower was the first one in the Cathedral and was built by Juan Lozano and Juan Serrano between 1651 to 1660.¹³

The Metropolitan Tabernacle was created by Lorenzo Rodríguez (1704-1774) that also done the Metropolitan Tabernacle.¹⁴ He followed the Mexican baroque with magnificent *churrigueresca* front¹⁵, the presence of baroque *estípites* and the reddish stone called *tezontle*.

⁴ GAUVIN, Alexander Bailey. *Art of Colonial Latin America*. United States: Phaidon, 2005, p. 264

⁵ ROCHA, Xavier Cortês. *El classicismo em la arquitetura mexicana 1524-1784*. México: MAPorrúa, 2007, p.191

⁶ GAUVIN, Alexander Bailey. *Art of Colonial Latin America*. United States: Phaidon, 2005, p. 264

⁷ Idem

⁸ Ibidem, p.10

⁹ Ibidem, p. 14

¹⁰ GAUVIN, Alexander Bailey. *Art of Colonial Latin America*. United States: Phaidon, 2005, p. 306

¹¹ ROCHA, Xavier Cortês. *El classicismo em la arquitetura mexicana 1524-1784*. México: MAPorrúa, 2007, p.191

¹² Ibidem, p. 193

¹³ ROCHA, Xavier Cortês. *El classicismo em la arquitetura mexicana 1524-1784*. México: MAPorrúa, 2007, p. 197

¹⁴ GALINDO, Carmen; GALINDO, Magdalena. *Mexico City Historic Center*. Mexico City: Ediciones Nueva Guía, pp 128-130 (site: www.enacademic.com, in: October 25th, 2014),2002, pp. 128-130

¹⁵ ROCHA, Xavier Cortês. *El classicismo em la arquitetura mexicana 1524-1784*. México: MAPorrúa, 2007, p.255

The main entrance at the principal façade was created in two parts, the first completed at 1672 which followed the classical construction: presence of arc, four Doric columns and with places to set the images between these columns.¹⁶

The second part was added with the baroque elements and fit harmoniously with the Classical style. The Baroque was represented in the façade by the presence of the Salomon's columns, the pillar in *estípites*, geometrical forms, and movement in the composition.

The architectural construction and the façade at the Cathedral make this building very important in the context of the political scene as an urban scenography.

References

GALINDO, Carmen; GALINDO, Magdalena. *Mexico City Historic Center*. Mexico City: Ediciones Nueva Guia, pp 128-130 (site: www.enacademic.com, in: October 25th, 2014),2002, pp. 128-130

GAUVIN, Alexander Bailey. *Art of Colonial Latin America*. United States: Phaidon, 2005

NOBERG-SCHULZ, Christian. *Arquitectura Barroca*. Madrid: Aguilar, 1972.

ROCHA, Xavier Cortês. *El classicismo em la arquitetura mexicana 1524-1784*. México: MAPorrúa, 2007

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, p.198